

**PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS
CONSTRUCTIVIST APPROACH OF TEACHING****Ms. Shaista Rahman**

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Abstract

The field of education has undergone a significant shift in thinking about the nature and process of human learning in order to optimize the degree and quality of meaningful learning. This requires change in teaching learning process which will develop higher order thinking among students. Constructivism is one of such approach which fulfills the need of this demand from the education process. It has gained significant attention in the past twenty years among the teaching community across the world.

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The present study addresses the pedagogical philosophy of prospective teachers of SNDT Women's University. The study aimed at examining the attitude of prospective teachers towards constructivist pedagogy. Data was collected from 152 prospective teachers. The rating scale on Teacher's Attitude towards Constructivist Approach in Teaching (TASCAT) developed by S. Lyngdoh and S.M Sungoh (2017) was used for the present study. The research revealed that majority of the prospective teachers (75.66 %) have moderate and (24.34 %) of the prospective teachers have high range of attitude towards constructivist pedagogy. However, there is no significant difference in Attitude towards constructivist approach on the basis of type of college, age, educational qualification, stream and marital status of the prospective teachers.

Key words- *Cconstructivist teaching, Prospective teachers' attitude towards constructivist approach, Prospective tteachers' ppedagogical philosophy.*

Introduction

Constructivism as epistemology is based on the premise that people construct their knowledge, skills and attitudes of the world through experiencing things and reflecting on those experiences, therefore knowledge cannot simply be transmitted from one person to another. New knowledge is constructed on the basis of prior knowledge and personal life experience as a result of targeted activities in a particular situation. It says that people construct their own understanding and knowledge of the world, through experiencing things and reflecting on those experiences (Bereiter, 1994). In other words, students actively construct knowledge by fitting new information upon the foundation of previous learning. Constructivist learning theory mainly then focuses on teaching students ‘how to learn’ skills to become autonomous learners (Gray, 1997). Constructivist classrooms differs from traditional classrooms in following ways-

Traditional Classroom	Constructivist Classroom
Curriculum is presented part to whole, with emphasis on basic skills.	Curriculum is presented whole to part with emphasis on big concepts
Strict adherence to fixed curriculum is highly valued	Pursuit of student questioning is highly valued
Curricular activities rely heavily on textbooks and workbooks	Curricular activities rely heavily on primary sources of data and manipulative materials
Students are viewed as “blank slates” onto which information is etched by the teacher	Students are viewed as thinkers with emerging theories about the world
Teachers generally behave in a didactic manner, disseminating information to students	Teachers generally behave in an interactive manner, mediating the environment for students
Teacher seeks the correct answer to validate student learning	Teachers seek the student’s point of view in order to understand student’s present conceptions for use in subsequent lessons
Assessment of student learning is viewed as separate from teaching and occurs almost entirely through testing	Assessment of student learning is interwoven with teaching and occurs through teacher observations of students at work and through student exhibitions and portfolios
Students primarily work alone.	Students primarily work in group.

(Source: Brooks and Brooks, 1993, p.17)

Traditional teaching has many disadvantages. Even if students (taught in the traditional way) score well on standardized tests, they are often unable to use memorized facts and formulae in real-life applications outside school (Boaler, 1998; Yager, 1991). They are unaware about the applicability of the school knowledge in real world and forget their rote learning over time (Yager, 1991).

Constructivist Approach And Its Application In Teaching

Constructivist approach as an emerging trend. In the constructivist classrooms, focus is on the students. Students are active learners involved in their own process of learning. Teacher act as facilitator and guide by helping them develop and assess their learning. There is a need to change the roles of the teachers from imparters of knowledge to facilitators of learning and the roles of the learners must also be changed from passive listener to active learners. Constructivism is a promising approach for bringing about this change. National Curriculum Framework (NCF) has also highlighted the importance of constructivism in Indian classroom situation. It is very important to know about the attitude of prospective teachers towards constructivist approach in teaching as their attitude affects students in many ways and can shape their learning experience. A favorable attitude of prospective teachers towards constructivist approach will facilitate the successful implementation of constructivist teaching in their classrooms whereas an unfavorable attitude will hinder its application in classroom situations. In SNDT university student teachers are expected to design constructivist lesson plans and implement it in classroom practices as one of the important aspects of their curriculum of B.Ed. program. Researcher is also a Ph.D. student of SNDT Women's university so was keen to understand the attitude of prospective teachers towards constructivist approach.

Objectives Of The Study

The study was conducted with following objectives:

1. To study the level of attitude towards Constructivist approach among the prospective teachers.
2. To compare the attitude of prospective teachers towards Constructivist approach on the basis of type of college.
3. To compare the attitude of prospective teachers towards Constructivist approach on the basis of their age.

4. To compare the attitude of prospective teachers towards constructivist approach on the basis of their educational qualification.
5. To compare the attitude of prospective teachers towards constructivist approach on the basis of their stream / faculty.
6. To compare the attitude of prospective teachers towards constructivist approach on the Basis Of Their Marital Status.

Methodology Of The Study

This is a descriptive study where survey was conducted to find out attitude of prospective teachers towards constructivist approach. Data was collected from prospective teachers of SNDT Women’s University, Mumbai.

Sample For The Study

The sample consisted of 152 prospective teachers from B.Ed. colleges viz *PVDT College of Education* for Women, *Aishabai College of Education* and **Mumbai B. Ed College for Women**. These are the three B.Ed. colleges affiliated to SNDT Women’s University and are located in Mumbai.

Table 1.1 indicates distribution of sample on the basis of demographic characteristics such as age, educational qualification, stream, type of college and marital status of prospective teachers.

Table 1. Sample distribution on the basis demographic characteristics

Age	N	Educational Qualification	N	Stream / Faculty	N	College type	N	Marital Status	N
< 30	140	Graduate	69	Arts	96	Aided	82	Married	44
> 30	12	Post Graduate	83	Other than Arts	56	Unaided	70	Unmarried	108

Data Collection

The researcher first obtained permission from the principals of the B.Ed. colleges and went there on the given date and time to collect the data. The data was collected from the final year

B.Ed. students only.

Research Instrument And Procedure

Teacher's Attitude Scale towards Constructivist Approach in Teaching (TASCAT) developed by S. Lyngdoh and S.M. Sungoh (2017) has been used for the present study. It consists of 40 items. The dimensions of the Scale are: (i) Reflection (ii) Learning Process (iii) Autonomy-Community (iv) Authority-Facilitator; (v) Power-Empowerment and (vi) Evaluation. TASCAT is a Likert type five-point Rating Scale which has the responses as Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The scores for positive statements are '4', '3', '2', '1', '0' and for negative statements the scores are in reverse order.

Results And Discussion

1. Level of Attitude towards Constructivist Approach

Level of Attitude of the Prospective Teachers of SNTD Women's University towards Constructivist Approach in teaching

Range of Scores	Level of Attitude	N	Percentage (%)
0-55	low	0	0
56-110	moderate	115	75.66
111-160	high	37	24.34
Total		152	

The above table and graph indicate the level of attitude of prospective teachers of SNDT Women's University towards constructivist approach in teaching. It shows that majority of the sample (75.66%) have moderate level of attitude and 24.34% have a high level of attitude towards constructivist approach. However, low level of attitude towards constructivist approach in teaching was not found among the prospective teachers of SNDT Women's University. This means that the prospective teachers have favorable attitude towards constructivist approach.

2. Type of College and Attitude towards Constructivist Approach

Type of College	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Level of significance
Aided	82	102.35	12.33	1.60	Not significant
Unaided	70	98.97	13.47		

The above table indicates that the value of 't' is found to be 'not significant'. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference in the attitude towards Constructivist approach among prospective teachers of aided and unaided colleges.

3. Age and Attitude towards Constructivist Approach

Age	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Level of significance
≤ 30 years	140	100.47	13.01	1.10	Not significant
>30 years	12	104.58	12.36		

The above table indicates that the value of 't' is found to be 'not significant'. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected. It is concluded that there is no significant difference in the attitude towards Constructivist approach in teaching among prospective teachers of less than or equal to 30 and more than 30 years of age.

4. Educational Qualification and Attitude towards Constructivist Approach

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Level of significance
Graduate	69	100.33	12.78	0.40	Not significant
Post-graduate	83	101.18	13.18		

The above table indicates that the value of 't' is found to be 'not significant'. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference among graduate and post-graduate prospective teachers in relation to their attitude towards Constructivist approach.

5. Stream and Attitude towards Constructivist Approach

Stream	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Level of significance
Arts	96	101.36	12.87	0.70	Not significant
Other than Arts	56	99.82	13.18		

The value of 't' is found to be 'not significant'. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference among prospective teachers of arts and other than arts stream in relation to their attitude towards Constructivist approach in teaching.

7. Marital status and Attitude towards Constructivist Approach

Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Level of significance
Married	44	99.72	11.88	0.68	Not Significant
Unmarried	108	101.23	13.41		

The above table indicates that the value of 't' is found to be 'not significant'. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference between married and unmarried prospective teachers in relation to their attitude towards Constructivist approach in teaching.

The attitude of prospective teachers towards constructivist approach of teaching is found to be favorable and there is no significant difference in attitude of prospective teachers on the basis

of their age, educational qualification, stream, type of college and marital status. The reason behind this favorable attitude may be due to their exposure towards constructivist approach. B.Ed. students of SNTD Women's University have constructivism in their syllabus of B.Ed. both as theory as well as practical.

Conclusion

India is a rapidly changing country in which inclusive, high-quality education is of utmost importance for its future prosperity. Constructivist model of teaching is proven to be effectual and contemporary enough to guarantee quality education that can promote holistic development in society (Essien & Undie,2018). Most of the prospective teachers of SNTD Women's University have shown moderate to high level of attitude towards Constructivist Approach in teaching. Favorable attitude will help in application of constructivist teaching in their classrooms. However, with more knowledge about this approach and more practical experiences of applying constructivist teaching methods, prospective teachers will become more proficient and willing to successfully implement this approach in real classroom situations. Thus, it will contribute towards the improvement of the quality of education which will hopefully provide all learners with capabilities they require *to* become economically productive, develop sustainable livelihoods, *contribute to* peaceful and democratic societies and enhance individual well-being.

References

- Bereiter C. (1994) Constructivism, socio-culturalism and Popper's World 3. *Educational Researcher*,23(7),21-23.
- Best, W. John & Kahn, V.J(2006) *Research in Education*. PHI Learning Private Limited, India.
- Boaler, J. (1998) Alternative approaches to teaching, learning and assessing mathematics. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 21(2), 129-141.
- Brooks, J.G. & Brooks, M.G. (1993) *In search of understanding: The case of constructivist classrooms*. Alexandria, V.A: Association for Supervision and Development.
- Essien, E.E., & Undie, J.B. (2018) *Promoting Quality Education in Social Studies Through Constructivist Teaching Model*.
- Gray, A. (1997) *Constructivist teaching and learning*. SSTA Research Centre Report, 97-07.
- Lyngdoh, S., & Sungoh, S. (2017) *Attitude of Student Teachers towards Constructivist Approach in Teaching*. *IRA International Journal of Education and Multidisciplinary*

- Studies (ISSN 2455-2526), 7(2), 83-88. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jems.v7.n2.p4>
- Lyngdoh, S., & Sungoh, S.M. (2017) Construction and Standardization of Teacher's Attitude Scale towards Constructivist Approach in Teaching (TASCAT). Educational Quest: An Int. J. of Education and Applied Social Science: Vol. 8, Special Issue, pp. 305-308. DOI: 10.5958/2230-7311.2017.00068.X
- Mohapatra, J.K, Mahapatra, M & Parida, B.K. (2015) Constructivism-The New Paradigm. Atlantic Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi.
- NCERT (2005) National Curriculum framework-2005. Publishing department, New Delhi: NCERT.
- Yager, R. E. (1991) The Constructivist Learning Model: Toward Real Reform in Science Education" dalam. The Science Teacher, 56(6).
<https://wenr.wes.org/2018/09/education-in-india>